

Basic education and youth employment in Odukpani local government area of cross River State

Ogar Ohiamia Ochagu ^{1,*}, Ndiyo Ndem Ayara ², Augustine Ele Asor ¹ and Etorti Imoke John ³

¹ Department of Economics University of Education and Entrepreneurship, Akamkpa-Nigeria.

² Department of Economics University of Calabar, Calabar Nigeria.

³ Department of Mathematics University of Education and Entrepreneurship, Akamkpa-Nigeria.

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Abstract

The paper examines the comparative impact of Formal (Basic Education) and Informal Education on rural development in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. It is argued that Basic Education will not translate into an engine of growth and rural development, except it is tailored and adapted to meet the needs of specific rural communities. There is therefore need for Basic Education programs by the Government, to be tailored to meet the needs of different rural communities, otherwise it will have an almost zero impact on development. The specific objectives were to examine the impact of access to Basic (formal) Education opportunity on rural development: and also, to find out the impact of acquisition of Non - formal Education through life skill acquisition on rural development in terms of human capital development and youth employment. Human capital development theory and structural model constituted the theoretical framework. Three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and a well-structured questionnaire was used to obtain quantitative data from 400 respondents, using a multi-stage sampling procedure. The field data were analyzed using one-way Analysis of Variance ANOVA technique. On hypothesis one; the result revealed that the calculated F-value of 50.149* is higher than the critical F-value of 2.10 at 0.05 level of significance with 399 degrees of freedom, for hypothesis two, the result showed the calculated F-value of 63.424* is higher than the critical F-value of 2.01 at 0.05 level of significance with 399 degrees of freedom, under hypothesis three, the result revealed the calculated F-value of 10.849* is higher than the critical F-value of 1.52 at 0.05 level of significance with 399 degrees of freedom; which implies that Basic-Nine Education, Acquisition of skills and Formal Basic-Nine Education has significant influence on employment opportunities/income generation, and acquisition of life skills in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State and therefore, very strategic for the development of rural areas. It was recommended, among others, that an accessible educational system in a conducive school environment with skill acquisition programmes should be promoted in order to enhance human capital development, labour productivity and gainful employment opportunities in rural areas.

Keywords: Basic Education; Youth employment; Income generation; Skills acquisition and Rural development

1. Introduction

The pre-colonial economy of Nigeria was highly diversified in nature. Apart from the people's traditional economy which was agriculture and associated activities such as hunting and fruit gathering, trade and Commerce formed part of the nation's means of livelihood. However, transcending these economic activities were local crafts and industries like soap making, cloth weaving, blacksmithing and pottery production, (Erinosho & Osunkoya, 2013) Due to the incessant raids for slaves and foodstuffs, this thriving indigenous economy underwent severe erosion and the local producers were all but forced to stop production.

* Corresponding author: Ogar Ohiamia Ochagu

The euphoria of independence that greeted Nigeria in 1960, called for more graduates to fill the vacuums created by the outgoing Colonial masters. So, immediately after 1960, the nation relied completely on education to move forward. Hence, education had to be planned so as to meet the manpower need of the nation. Citizens who were educated as at the period were employed to fill in the existing vacancies and majority of them became front line personalities in the nation. This social class upward migration appealed to Nigerians especially the parents and they patronized formal education as a source of White-collar jobs. School enrolment increased astronomically. The available manpower, infrastructural facilities such as classrooms, chair and tables, school library, etc., and instructional materials such as audio, visual, and audio-visual as well as general funds were inadequate to cater for the increased students' enrollment. These resulted to a notable falling standard of education in the Nigerian education system.

Nevertheless, as the population of the nation and that of the educated elites was increasing, the probability of getting jobs was also reducing. Most of the students after graduating from rural schools migrated to the cities in search of jobs. This resulted to overcrowdings in Nigerian major cities. Hence, the major cities became amphitheatres of struggle for survival. It is obvious that if education is locally controlled, practically applied in problem solving, and focused on functional specialization, it can and will contribute to rural development in developing countries.

Mangda and Mukherjee (2018), although, the distinction between rural and urban areas is usually not bi-modal, but on a continuum, the differences between the standard of living in rural area and urban center can be stark. Since the greater proportion of the people in Nigeria lives in rural environments, therefore, rural development is a key factor in the overall economic development in the country. Unfortunately, the contribution of rural areas to the national economic development is usually limited, especially in developing countries. Rural areas usually experience wide varieties of social, economic, political, and moral challenges such as lower per capita income, lower educational level, fewer employment opportunities, limited educational and cultural facilities, confined social environments, migration, less developed health services, fewer commercial facilities, declined small towns, and less confidence in the future prospects. One of the major inequalities affecting the rural poor is their unequal access to quality education, which is so important for social and economic development. The vast majority of the rural poor depend on agriculture for their livelihoods.

It is difficult for a community to foster development without an educated population. Education oriented on urban needs has accelerated rural to urban migration and has not done much in developing rural areas. The colonial type of elementary, secondary and college education in many countries has created white collar employment expectations which are often difficult to meet and has also distorted the concept of education for rural development. Because of this type of educational programs, youth unemployment rates have alarmingly increased in rural areas in many developing countries.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Education has a desirable controlling influence over development of the rural individual, family, community, and society, leading to reduced poverty, income equity, and controlled unemployment. Basic education is the foundational educational level offered at preschool elementary levels, and junior high school levels. (Denman, C., 2019). It thus comprises both formal schooling (primary and junior secondary schools) as well as a wide variety of non-formal and informal public and private educational activities offered to meet the defined basic learning needs of groups of people of all ages. It is one of the most powerful weapons in the fight against rural poverty and for rural development. The philosophy behind the 9years Basic Education system of the present-day Nigeria is reductionism and prevention of the school drop-out scenario which has been encapsulating the Nigerian Schools.

In the past, many students do drop-out from schools before getting to the Basic Nine (formally Jss3). They usually stop after obtaining primary school leaving certificate at primary six (presently Basic Six). This menace had the crippling effect of preventing young Nigerians from being self-reliant. Therefore, the ideological philosophy behind Basic Education is to make the minimum qualification in Nigeria: "Basic Nine Certificate". This is to ensure that every citizen is self-reliant, as well as to spark the required Socio-economic fundamentals required for growth and development. It was for this reason that this study was carried out; to find out if basic education has the potential to predict rural development in Odukpani Local Government Area, of Cross River State. The specific basic education services considered included promoting access to formal education and non-formal education through promotion of life skill acquisition, development and food security. Naturally, this stance must be adopted first at the level of basic education.

Moreover, existing studies in Cross River State did not correlate basic education with rural development in Odukpani Local Government Area, therefore this study filled up the gap in this domain. The study was thus, mainly concerned with the educational component in rural development.

Objectives of the study

The major objective of the study was to investigate the impact of basic education on rural development in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study sought to:

- Examine the impact of access to formal education (basic nine) on employment opportunities/income generation in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State.
- Examine the impact of non-formal education through life skill acquisition on employment opportunities/income generation in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State.
- Examine the comparative impact of formal and non-formal education, on employment/ income generation in Odukpani local Government area of Cross River State.

1.2. Statement of hypotheses

The following hypothesis were formulated to guide the study.

- **Hypothesis One:** Access to Basic-Nine Education has no significant influence on employment opportunities/income generation in Odukpani Local Government Area, Cross River State.
- **Hypothesis Two:** Acquisition of life skills has no significant influence on employment opportunities/enhanced incomes in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State.
- **Hypothesis Three:** Formal Basic-Nine Education has a significantly greater influence on employment/Income generation than Acquisition of life skills in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State.

2. Literature Review

The diverse types of society whether patriarchal, slave-based, feudal, capitalist, or socialist have systems of education which differ from each other in varying degrees. Accordingly, in traditional societies, the elders' hand down knowledge of what the younger generation need to know to ensure their livelihood and the continuity of their family, clan, and tribe. Although the traditional society has no formal school this does not mean that it has no education. Coombs and Ahmed, in Smith M. K. (2002) defined formal education as an institutionalized, chronologically graded and hierarchically structured educational system spanning lower primary school to upper reaches of the university; and a non-formal education as any organized, systematic learning activity undertaken outside the framework of formal school system to provide various types of learning opportunities to particular sub-groups in the population. Since the main purpose of formal and non-formal education is to impart behavioral knowledge to its immediate clientele, the term education has been used here as a common term throughout this paper for informal as well as formal education. It is clear that different forms of education result from different socio-economic, cultural and political systems of a country, (Cambell, 2006)

Education is both the product of society as well as an important tool for bringing about changes in the rural community. There is a dialectical relationship between education and society. Rural development and educational development are inseparable. Education encourages involvement of individuals from the cradle to the grave in imparting knowledge. Thus, all citizens are well aware of the important of education for their life, and that education should be given a first and foremost place in the services of a democracy which demands not only that the people be protected against arbitrary decisions but also that they take part in decisions making process which affect the future of their society, (Coladarci, 2007).

Basic education has long been recognized as a potential means for rural development. According to the National Population commission, (2012), it was projected that Nigeria had a population of about 170 million. Of this number, 67% were believed to reside in rural areas, while the remaining 33% lived in urban areas. In many developing countries, education has been seen as a panacea for national development, (World Bank, 2000). The education system is considered as a key factor in the rapid sectorial, regional, and national development in many developing countries. It has been argued that a well-supported, easily accessible educational system is an efficient means to make people economically conscious, and therefore, make them to actively participate in their economic prosperity and cultural advancement.

Education also increases the physical ability of rural people to diagnose their needs, assert their rights, and take greater control of decisions affecting their lives. In spite of the negative role education played in some countries, rural development planners and leaders still believe that education is a primary means to promote cultural and socio-economic development among their citizens, (Sajjad, 2019). Education in rural areas takes place at many different levels, from multi-grade primary schools to agricultural universities. In many countries social change and economic

development have been organized by providing not only basic education (which is acknowledged as a priority), but also specific training to improve techniques employed in the rural economy.

A typical rural system is characterized as having seven functional components, related to each other through a linkage of infrastructure connected to a social, political, economic, religious, cultural, and physical environment, (Nytes and Musegades, 1985). The functional components are supply, production, marketing, personnel maintenance, education, health care, and governance. A change in any of these components affects all the other components and all aspects of the rural system. However, education component plays a unique role as facilitator of transactions for all linkages, and serves to enhance frequency, fidelity, and capacity of the linkages in the rural development "processes, (Miller and Merritt, 1985).

Adapting primary education to the specific needs of the rural population is aimed to provide functional education and training in order to give children a better knowledge of their environment and to teach them the farming trade. In the 1960s and 1970s, the numerous debates over the role played by education in the growth of agricultural output led to the adoption of a set of reforms in educational systems. In 1975, the International Institute for Educational Planning (IIEP) suggested that a distinction be made between the 'ruralization of programmes and the 'ruralization of education'. While former refers to an overhaul of existing school programmes to promote the acquisition of agricultural skills, the latter term embodied various measures to provide rural areas with schools, so that all children who live in them receive basic education. It may be noted that this distinction was not taken up in the literature on the subject, which indicates not only a certain ambiguity in the notion of 'ruralization' but also the gradual shift from the concept of agricultural education to that of basic education in rural areas. The main objective of these reforms was to bring schools closer to the rural areas not only by instruction in agricultural techniques but also by the use of new teaching methods.

These policies have often been referred to collectively as 'ruralization', but this is in fact a term that recalls certain practices used under the colonial regime. During the colonial period, ruralization of education was one of the two facets of the colonial strategy: humanistic education to prepare the elites and the staff of the colonial administration; a second track of practically oriented education for the rural population. In the post-independence context, this concept does not reflect the complexity of the efforts to adopt an educational approach that ensures the relevance of education to its environment without the discriminatory purpose explicit in the colonial 'ruralization' strategies, (Coladarci, 2007)

In the early 1970s, several countries, (Rwanda, Malawi, Burundi, and Ethiopia) received support from the World Bank to overhaul their school programmes in order to make them more relevant to rural development by introducing practical subjects. The purpose of this strategy was to better integrate schools into the rural environment by developing knowledge and practical skills in line with the requirements of the rural population and by preserving local values. Summarizing these efforts, the 1982 Conference of Ministers of Education and Ministers responsible for Economic Planning of the Member States of Africa observed that, educational policies since the late 1960s reflect a concern with putting education, at all levels, at the service of agricultural and rural development. More generally, many developing countries tried to adapt schools to the rural environment and to agricultural activities.

It must be given a 'rural' orientation to encourage more pupils to pursue agricultural activities, in order to foster the development of rural areas and as a result to curb migration to the cities. It is accepted that farmers with basic education are more likely to adopt new technology and become more productive. With basic education they are better equipped to make more informed decisions for their lives and for their communities and to be active participants in promoting the economic, social and cultural dimensions of development. It is equally accepted that excess rural labour has to find work outside the farm, whether in rural or urban settings and that without basic literacy and numeracy, individuals are unlikely to be hired for anything more than basic wage labour.

As early as 1967, the 'Arusha Declaration' presented community schools as a way of creating an education system corresponding to the requirements of agriculture, the dominant sector of economic activity. Primary education was to be practical, utilitarian. The idea was to integrate the school into the surrounding community by establishing a two-way relationship: pupils participate in work in the fields, in road construction, etc. and parents become familiar with school activities as part of a large-scale literacy programme. In addition, parents participate in school construction, programme development, etc. The main idea behind community schools was that they usually occupy a central position within the village in order to put itself fully at the service of the community; and the education of children should be linked to that of adults. (Gasperini, 1999, 2000). In this perspective, the content of school programmes should be based on the real needs of the community.

The (World Economic forum, 2016) suggested three channels through which education affects a country's productivity. First, it increases the collective ability of the workforce to carry out existing tasks more quickly. Secondly, secondary

and tertiary education especially, facilitates the transfer of knowledge about new information, products and technologies created by others. (Barro and Lee, 2010). Finally, by increasing creativity, it boosts a country's own capacities to create its own knowledge, products and technologies. Another strategy for broadening access to primary education in rural areas was to introduce more flexibility in the way schools' function. This was done by establishing new primary education structures that were more flexible than the traditional norms and framework. Resorting to multilevel classes, for example, makes it possible to bring provision to areas of low population density.

In the rural environment, the so-called 'double-shift' system — giving a teacher two groups of pupils, one in the morning and the other in the afternoon — allows pupils to continue to participate in household economic activities. This reduces the opportunity cost of sending children to school and thus helps to improve retention rates. Along the same lines, flexible school hours were frequently introduced in rural areas in order to make the school schedule correspond to the daily and seasonal cycles of agricultural production. The educational reform in Benin in 1977, for example, introduced a modification of the school calendar to bring it into harmony with the agricultural calendar.

The idea of a continuum encompassing formal, non-formal and informal education, which is widely accepted today in the context of lifelong learning, has its roots in the well-known distinction made by (Coombs, 1975). Non-formal education is defined as "any organized and systematic educational activity situated outside of the traditional education system and aimed at providing certain types of education to specific population groups, adults as well as children". Informal education is characterized by "unstructured learning stemming from one's own daily experience and contacts with one's own socio-economic milieu". One of the objectives of non-formal education is to expand the learning opportunities of children not enrolled in the traditional school system and to meet the needs of the population more effectively. The multiplicity of forms and the flexibility of non-formal education are major assets that promote the adaptation of programmes to various rural contexts. Non-formal education projects are characterized by great diversity, in terms of teaching methods, the subjects taught financing, objectives, target population and the qualifications of teaching staff.

As far back as the 1970s, it was already considered that rural communities must change their behaviour with respect to progress and play an active role in driving development ('co-operative self-help'). Rural development thus demands an integrated approach which, in addition to facilitating access to education and to new technologies, mobilizes a range of factors such as access to credit, to transportation, to health, etc.

(Coombs and Manzoor, 1974). Throughout the world, a great many projects and studies have been conducted with a view to enabling education to play its role in the agricultural and rural development of developing countries. The results have been mixed: some projects have borne fruit, while others have not obtained the expected results despite governments' genuine will to succeed and the support of international organizations and NGOs.

Thirty years after the debates of the 1970s on the role of education in rural development, it is striking that the same questions are coming up again. Today, however, the international context is no longer the same. Over the last ten years or so, the global environment has been undergoing a radical transformation, in particular the expansion of the market economy and the growing interdependence of countries and policies in the context of globalization. In this new context, it seems necessary to reexamine the question of educational development through the new problems of rural development and food security. Naturally, this stance must be adopted first at the level of basic education. What level of formal education is needed for economic growth? The United Nations Millennium Development Goals focused on Universal Primary education. Though important, Primary education alone is regarded as insufficient. (Grant, 2017). Universal Primary Education must be complemented with the goal of ensuring that large sections of the population complete at least junior secondary education (IIASA, 2008).

2.1. Theoretical Framework

2.1.1. Structural Model

The structural model is associated with (Claessens and David, 1993). The model posits that the development of the rural economy is hinged on the development of viable structural and institutional framework. The prime focus is on the transformation of major institutions and structures of the society. The model stresses that if these structures are transformed in line with modern or western democratic ideas, the society will develop. In terms of rural development, it is to restructure and improve upon the existing economic, social, educational and other institutional structures of the rural economy to meet the needs of the people and help transform their lives for the better.

According to the structural model, improving the infrastructure of the rural educational sub-sector is significant in improving the lives of the rural dwellers. Evidence lies in advanced nations that developing educational structures can be effective in improving the overall performance of other sub-sector of the rural economy. This model strongly asserts that developing a specific sector of the economy can have a radiating influence or a rippling effect on other sub-sectors.

The model is relevant in this study. It implies that basic education has elements of liberation because of its emphasis on the whole broad range of educational activities (both formal and non-formal) occurring in different settings to meet the learning needs. It means restructuring education in its basic form through providing conducive school environment, promoting access to education, promotion of non-formal aspect through life skills acquisition, etc, have the potential to foster rural development in terms of improved human capital, labour productivity in agriculture, employment creation, mass literacy, political awareness, enhanced incomes of rural people, etc. The model recognizes the role of education in rural development by its impact and observes that by increasing the quality and quantity of education in rural areas private and public investors can be attracted.

2.2. Human Capital Theory

The development theoreticians of the 1960s viewed agricultural growth as the principal force driving a nation's development. For example, some development authors argue that if agriculture is in a slump, it offers only a stagnant market and hampers the development of the rest of the economy. If agricultural development is neglected, it becomes more difficult to develop anything else: this is the fundamental principle of balanced growth (Lewis, 1954). The idea that agriculture plays an important role in the overall economic growth of developing countries seems to be confirmed by the existence of a correlation between increased agricultural yields and increases in total output.

Human capital theory regards education as an investment "like any other", and as a generator of externalities. For example, individuals make individual choices concerning their education, but this choice has a strong economic impact through the resulting increase in total factor productivity. The role of human capital in a country's growth was the subject of prolonged debate, and a number of authors have tried to provide an empirical demonstration of the relation between education and agricultural productivity in developing countries. (Lockheed, Jamison and Lau, 1980); (Phillips, 1994); and (Mook, 1973; 1981).

According to human capital theory, the educational level of the rural labour force has an influence on agricultural productivity. This relationship may take three forms: education can improve the quality of farmers' labour by enabling them to produce more with their available stock of production factors (other than labour); education can increase the efficiency of resource allocation; education can help farmers to choose more effective means of production by adopting new techniques.

(Berstecher, 1985) argued that education 'planned' in conventional ways tends to be dysfunctional to rural development, and therefore, there is a need in planning today to take a fresh look at the social and political question of how learning needs can best be determined and met. However, empirical studies conducted to confirm the existence of the education productivity relationship should be regarded with caution, as levels of education and productivity can be difficult to measure. The theory implies that education plays a greater role in total factor productivity. It builds the rural capacity for functional living and thus, creating a conducive learning environment, ensuring access to formal education and non-formal education have the potential to improve quality of rural life. (Schultz, 1988) observes that education explains the greater part of total factor productivity. The theory can be adapted to other skill acquisition, other than agriculture.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

It was a survey design where attempt was made to observe the impact of basic education (independent variable) on provision of conducive school environment, promotion of access to education and apprenticeship training (non-formal education) on rural development (dependent variables) in terms of human capital development, labour productivity in agriculture, youth employment and enhanced income. This design enabled the researcher to make use of a questionnaire to elicit responses from respondents from the target population. Thus, the researcher was able to obtain data from both quantitative and qualitative sources.

3.2. Study Area

Odukpani Local Government Area was the study area. It is bounded to the North by Akamkpa Local Government Area and Abia State, west by Akwa Ibom State, East by Akpabuyo and South by Calabar Municipality Local Government. It covers an area of 2,624.66sq.km comprising thirteen (13) council wards, forty (40) clans and over five hundred (500) villages. Odukpani Local Government Area is characterized by diseases, ignorance, neglect and exploitations from inception. It has a large youthful population; 13 percent are children within the age bracket of 0-5 years while about 50 percent are within the age bracket of 6-40 years. This creates major challenges of childhood care and basic services, education, skill acquisition and employment generation.

3.3. Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised all the inhabitants of the thirteen (13) wards that make up Odukpani Local Government Area. The population is 192,884 (NPC, 2006), projected at 242,985 by 2015. All adult citizens of all works of life residing in this local government area and comprising those gainfully employed, farmers, fishermen, entrepreneurs, students and the unemployed, formed the study population. These people will be in a better position to provide reliable information.

3.4. Sample size

The sample size for the study was made up of 400 respondents selected from one third (1/3rd) of the wards in the local government. They comprised people from all works of life residing in the study area irrespective of their status in their communities. The sample size also included 8 teachers and 8 owners of apprenticeship workshops where non-formal educational activities take place. Thus, the total sample size was, 416. To determine the sample size, the simplified procedure recommended by Yamere (1967) was adopted. The sample of the study was made up of 400 respondents selected from four (4) wards (strata).

3.5. Sampling Procedure

The 13 wards constituted 13 major strata. The researcher selected one-third out of the total number of wards; that gave rise to four (4) wards which constituted the 4 minor strata. These wards were selected using the balloting method of simple random sampling. A hundred were selected out of each ward. The overall number of respondents was thus 400.

3.6. Instruments of data collection

The instrument used for data collection was the Basic Education and Rural Development Questionnaire. The questionnaire had 14 items and was divided into sections A and B. Section A elicited information on respondents' socio-demographic data while section B assessed the opinion of the participants on basic education. The section was further divided into three (3) sub-scales based on the objectives of the study. This involved eight (8) school teachers. Also, eight (8) owners of apprentice workshops where informal and non-informal educational activities take place were interviewed. Quantitative data were analyzed using chi-square while the qualitative data were thematically analyzed.

3.7. Analysis and Findings

Table 1 Socio-demographic information of respondents' variable

S/N0.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Sex Distribution		
	Male	189	47.25
	Female	211	52.75
	Total	400	100.00
2	Age Distribution		
	18-24	95	23.75
	25-30	61	15.25
	31-36	105	26.25
	37-42	87	21.75
	43 years and above	52	13.00

	Total	400	100.00
3	Level of Formal Education		
	Primary	193	48.25
	Secondary	129	32.25
	Tertiary	22	5.5
	No formal Education	56	14
	Total	400	100.00
4	Occupation		
	Civil Servant	34	8.5
	Farming	101	25.25
	Trading/Business	87	21.75
	Student	49	12.25
	Fishing	95	23.75
	Unemployed	34	8.5
	Total	400	100.00
5.	Marital Status		
	Single	159	39.75
	Married	171	42.75
	Separated/Divorced	70	17.50
	Total	400	100.00

Source: Field survey 2024

Table I indicates socio-demographic characteristics of respondents regarding sex distribution, age distribution, level of education, occupation, and marital status. Based on the table, more females, 211(52.75%) participated in the study. The highest age bracket was between 31- 36 with 105(26.25%). Majority of respondents had acquired formal education while 56(14%) were recipients of non-formal education. Majority of them too were farmers, 101(21.75%) and most of them were married 171(42.75%).

- **Hypothesis One:** Access to Basic-Nine Education has no significant influence on employment opportunities/income generation in Odukpani Local Government Area, Cross River State.

Table 2 Responses on Basic-Nine Education and Employment Opportunities/Income Generation

S/NO.:	Items	SA	A	total	%	D	SD	total	%
1	Access to Basic-Nine Education has made me more effective at my present employment?	110	120	230	57.5	90	80	170	42.5
2	I think Basic Education is really necessary for any kind of employment?	202	70	272	68.0	84	44	128	32.0
3	Having had access to Basic Education, I can grasp new skills more easily on my job?	132	154	286	71.5	24	90	114	28.5
4	Access to Basic-Nine Education makes me more effective at my job than my counterparts who have none?	190	50	240	60.0	60	100	160	40.0
5	I do not think further Education than the Basic-Nine level is necessary for me at my job?	170	74	244	61.0	81	75	156	39.0
	Grand means			1,272	63.6			728	36.4

Table 3 One-way ANOVA of the influence of access to Basic Education on employment opportunities/income generation

	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	842.734	6	140.456	50.145	0.00
Within Groups	1100.703	393	2.801		
Total	1943.438	399			

*Significant at 0.05 level, critical F=2.10, DF=399

The data of research question one, items number 1,2,3,4, and 5, as presented in Table 2, revealed the total number and percentage of acceptance responses in favor of research question one to be 1,272(63.6%) again the number of responses and percentage opposing the research question to be 728(36.4%), implying that Basic-Nine Education positively influences employment opportunities/income generation in the research area. The data in table 2 was subjected to one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), the result of data analysis in Table 3 revealed that the calculated F-value of 50.145* is higher than the critical F-value of 2.10 at 0.05 level of significance with 399 degrees of freedom. With this result the null hypothesis that access to Basic-Nine Education has no significant influence on employment opportunities/income generation in Odukpani Local Government Area, Cross River State was rejected. This implies that access to Basic-Nine Education has a significant influence on employment opportunities/income generation in the study area.

- **Hypothesis Two:** Acquisition of life skills has no significant influence on employment opportunities/enhanced incomes in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Table 4 Responses on Acquisition of life skills and employment opportunities/income

S/NO.	Items	SA	A	total	%	D	SD	total	%
6	I have no access to Basic-Nine Education but it has affected my job effectiveness?	140	122	262	65.5	97	41	138	34.6
7	Acquisition of life skills is a sufficient means of securing an employment?	247	40	287	71.75	50	63	113	28.25
8	I think it is waste of time to secure a Basic-Nine Education s it does not make me more employable?	84	110	194	48.5	80	126	206	51.5
9	I am better at my job than my colleagues with Basic-Nine Education?	191	58	249	62.25	40	111	151	37.75
10	I think having Basic-Nine Education will enhance my skills even further?	140	100	240	60.0	84	76	160	40.0
	Grand means			1,232	61.6			768	38.40

Table 5 One-way ANOVA of the influence of life skills on employment opportunities/enhanced incomes

	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	443.965	6	63.424*	16.581	0.00
Within Groups	1499.473	393	3.835		
Total	1943.437	399			

*Significant at 0.05 level, critical F=2.10, DF=399

In table 4, the number and percentages of responses in favor and against the research question two are 1,232(61.6%) and 768(38.40) respectively, meaning that life skills positively influence employment opportunities/enhanced incomes. These inferences were made from research question two items 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10, of the questionnaire. Again, the data in Table 4 was subjected to one-way ANOVA, the result of data analysis as presented in Table 5 revealed that the calculated F-value of 63.424* is higher than the critical F-value of 2.01 at 0.05 level of significance with 7 and 392 degrees of freedom. With this result the null hypothesis that acquisition of life skills has no significant influence on employment

opportunities/enhanced incomes in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State was rejected. This implies that acquisition of life skills has a significant influence on employment opportunities/income generation in the study area.

- **Hypothesis Three:** Formal Basic-Nine Education has a significantly greater influence on employment/Income generation than Acquisition of life skills in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Table 6 Responses on Formal Basic-Nine Education employment//income generation than and skill acquisition

S/NO.	Items	SA	A	total	%	D	SD	total	%
11	Enrolment into Basic-Nine classes has become steadily increasing?	199	70	269	67.25	80	51	131	32.75
12	There are very few or non-existent dropout of the Basic Nine classes?	90	99	189	47.25	104	107	211	52.75
13	Dropouts of the Basic-Nine classes are traceable to other reasons not loss of interest?	84	109	193	48.25	84	123	207	51.75
14	After successful completion of pre-Basic-Nine class, most pupils can find employment or income generating opportunity?	172	96	268	67.0	78	54	132	33.00
15	Most pupils continue ahead of Basic-Nine into higher classes and even Tertiary Institutions?	74	133	207	51.75	103	90	193	48.25
16	Most students who turn up for apprenticeship have had some degree of Basic-Education?	208	80	288	72.0	60	52	112	28.00
17	I think having had a Basic-Nine Education makes my apprentices easier to learn/teach?	94	100	194	48.5	101	105	206	51.50
18	I would rather accept an apprentice with a Basic-Nine Education than one who has none?	85	109	194	48.5	83	123	206	51.50
19	Apprentice with a Basic-Education do not usually do well in learning other life skills?	172	97	269	67.25	78	53	131	32.75
20	Apprentice with a Basic-Education are more successful when they graduate than those with no education?	101	134	235	58.75	75	90	165	41.25
	Total/Averages			2306	57.65			1,694	42.35

Again, in table 6, the number and percentages of responses in favor and against the research question three are 2306(67.65%) and 1,694(42.35%) respectively, meaning that formal Basic-Nine Education employment//income generation than and skill acquisition. These generalizations were reached at from research question two items 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20, of the research questionnaire. The result of data analysis in Table 7 revealed that the calculated F-value of 10.849* is higher than the critical F-value of 1.52 at 0.05 level of significance with 374 degrees of freedom. The Partial Eta-square of the analysis revealed both Basic Education and Acquisition of Life Skills has 81.9% influence on employment/Income generation. However, Basic Education alone has the greater influence of 40.8% on employment/income generation; which was found to be greater than that of Acquisition of life skills at 32.7%. With this result, the hypothesis that formal Basic-Nine Education has a significantly greater influence on employment/Income generation than Acquisition of life skills in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State was accepted. This implies that Basic-Nine Education has a significantly greater influence on employment opportunities/income generation than acquisition of life skills in the study area.

Table 7 Two-way ANOVA of the Impact of formal Basic Education and Acquisition of life skills on employment /Income Generation

F	DF ₁	DF ₂	Sig.			
10.849	25	374	0.00			
Source	Type III Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1591.052 ^a	25	63.642	67.546 60198.260 42.918	0.00 0.00 0.00	0.819
Intercept	56719.184	1	56719.184			0.994
Basic-Nine Education	242.628	6	40.438			0.408
Acquisition of life skills	171.066	7	24.438	25.937	0.00	0.327
Basic -Nine Education/Acquisition of life Skills	386.276	12	32.190	34.164	0.00	0.523
Error	352.385	374	0.942			
Total	279409.000	400				
Corrected Total	1943.438	399				

R-squared =0.819 (Adjusted R-squared=0.807) Design: Intercept + BASIC NINE EDUCATION + LIFE SKILLS + BASIC NINE EDUCATION*LIFE SKILLS

4. Discussion findings

This paper examines the comparative impact of Formal (Basic education) and Informal education on rural development in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. It is argued that basic education will not translate into an engine of growth and rural development, except it is tailored and adapted to meet the needs of specific rural communities. There is therefore need for basic education programs by the Government, to be tailored to meet the needs of different rural communities; otherwise it will have an almost zero impact on development.

Table I indicates socio-demographic characteristics of respondents regarding sex distribution, age distribution, level of education, occupation, and marital status. Based on the table, more females, 211(52.75%) participated in the study. The highest age bracket was between 31- 36 with 105(26.25%). Majority of respondents had acquired formal education while 56(14%) were recipients of non-formal education. Majority of them too were farmers, 101(21.75%) and most of them were married 171(42.75%).

The data in Table 2 was subjected to one-way Analysis of Variance, the result of data analysis in Table 3 revealed that the calculated F-value of 50.149* is higher than the critical F-value of 2.10 at 0.05 level of significance with 393 degrees of freedom. With this result the null hypothesis that access to Basic-Nine Education has no significant influence on employment opportunities/income generation in Odukpani Local Government Area, Cross River State was rejected. This implies that access to Basic-Nine Education has a significant influence on employment opportunities/income generation in the study area.

Similarly, the data in Table 4 was subjected to one-way ANOVA, the result of data analysis as presented in Table 5 revealed that the calculated F-value of 63.424* is higher than the critical F-value of 2.01 at 0.05 level of significance with 7 and 392 degrees of freedom. With this result the null hypothesis that acquisition of life skills has no significant influence on employment opportunities/enhanced incomes in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State was rejected. This implies that acquisition of life skills has a significant influence on employment opportunities/income generation in the study area.

Furthermore, the data in Table 6 was to one-way ANOVA, the result of data analysis as presented in Table 7 revealed that the calculated F-value of 10.849* is higher than the critical F-value of 1.52 at 0.05 level of significance with 374 degrees of freedom. The Partial Eta-square of the analysis revealed both Basic Education and Acquisition of Life Skills has 81.9% influence on employment/Income generation. However, Basic Education alone has the greater influence of

40.8% on employment/income generation; which was found to be greater than that of Acquisition of life skills at 32.7%. With this result, the hypothesis that formal Basic-Nine Education has a significantly greater influence on employment/Income generation than Acquisition of life skills in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State was accepted. This implies that Basic-Nine Education has a significantly greater influence on employment opportunities/income generation than acquisition of life skills in the study area.

The findings of the study revealed that basic education impacts on rural development. The findings here support (Coladarci, 2007) that rural development and educational development are symbiotically released and mutually reinforcing. Education has long been recognized as a potential means for activating rural development. (Miller and Memitt, 1985) had earlier reported that knowledge constitutes a key element for strengthening rural communities and facilitating their adaption to change. The findings also validate earlier report by (Catala, 1969) and (Lindsey, 1975) that the role of education in rural development is prominent by its impact on employment and income. Increasing the quantity and quality of education in rural areas can attract private and public investors into rural communities. Findings here are consistent with earlier evidence that the interaction of employment opportunities with basic education constitutes the whole economic progress in rural development.

It shows that basic educational services help to increase functional ability of rural people by promoting life skills. Education strengthens the rural people critical abilities thus enhancing their capacity to diagnose their own needs asserts their own rights and has greater control over the decisions that affect their lives. Basic education, provide rural areas with trained manpower resource. (Woessman, 2015) admitted based on available evidence, that education is a leading determinant of economic growth, employment and earnings. His findings support, (Sajjad, 2019) that education increases productivity of rural labour force.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Basic educational services and rural development tend to show much convergence in this study. Both domains now recognize similar intervention principles focusing on poverty reduction through human capital development, employment generation, enhanced labour productivity in agriculture etc. Rural dwellers are prepared for off-farms employment by building their knowledge and skills capacity. The non-formal education component has helped to expand the learning opportunities of people so as to meet the needs of a better quality of life. While there are various ideological perspectives on the role of basic education in the socio-economic development of rural communities, it is an established fact that basic education has a role to play in rural development which has to do with a transformation of the rural areas, alleviation of rural poverty, and enhancement of the quality of rural life, productivity and income. Basic education is the key to increasing efficiency in the rural economy since it has the potential to raise overall productivity and intellectual flexibility of the rural labour force. It increases people's productivity and creativity levels and acts as an instrument for security, social and economic progress.

The following recommendations were made:

- An accessible educational system should be promoted in a conducive environment as an efficient means of making people conscious and actively participate in rural and cultural development.
- Education should aim to provide equal access and opportunities for all, especially for girls and women since it is the only way of improving one's social position and standard of living.
- Since the interaction of job development with rural education constitutes the whole economic progress in rural development, efforts should be made to inculcate literacy and life skills for both children and adults.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

We sincerely declare that all the authors have participated in carrying out the research, evaluation and analysis of the research article and they have approved the final version. Also, there is no form of conflicts of interest in connection with this paper. Furthermore, the material described is not under publication or consideration for publication elsewhere

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain studies performed on animals/human subjects by any of the authors.

Statement of informed consent

Individuals who served as participants in the study were duly invited to participate in the study which involves survey and interview. Their participation in the study was voluntary and on mandate to withdraw at any given time without any form of oppression or duress nor consequences for withdrawal. The participants were assured of the confidentiality of the information provided and that it shall be used solely for academic purposes

By participating, the participants' therefore consent to the use of their responses for the study and were obligated to feel free to contact the researchers in case of any questions or clarifications needed about the research and were therefore not taken unaware.

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